

Review Report

Final Title: Carnosic Acid as a Promising Anticancer Agent: Mechanisms of Action and Therapeutic Potential Across Multiple Cancer Types

Submission Title: Anticancer Activity of Carnosic Acid: A Short Review

Submission Date: February 12, 2025

Initial Editorial Assessment: February 12, 2025

Sent for Review: February 12, 2025

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Round 1

<p>Reviewer 1 Name: Anonymous Conflict of Interest: None Date of Reviewer's Comments: February 22, 2025 Date of Author Response: March 11, 2025</p>	
Reviewer 1 Comments	Author Response
<p>Reviewer Recommendation: Revision Required Overview: In general, both the scientific content and writing quality of the present study are excellent. There aren't any fundamental issues with the article, but it would be strengthened by a few modifications and corrections.</p>	<p>Thank you for your suggestion. We appreciate your valuable time. We review it according to your comment.</p>
<p>In the abstract, the author mentioned, "Carnosic acid (CA), a phenolic diterpene, exhibits pharmacological actions" Please write this line as "multiple/different pharmacological actions" and mention some pharmacological properties here.</p>	<p>Thank you for your feedback. We have written it according to your suggestion in the revised manuscript.</p>
<p>In the introduction section, please include some name of the traditional treatment of cancer along with obstacles or limitations of traditional cancer treatment and how natural products help to overcome these obstacles.</p>	<p>Thank you for your suggestion. We have included it.</p>
<p>Add some keywords like "molecular mechanism" or "anticancer effects" instead of "breast cancer" or "lung cancer".</p>	<p>Thank you for your feedback. We have added these keywords.</p>
<p>Include some data on the pharmacological properties of Carnosic Acid.</p>	<p>Thank you for your comment. We added some data on pharmacological properties of Carnosic acid.</p>
<p>In the footnote of Table 1 add more abbreviations including AKT, SGK1, mTOR, etc.</p>	<p>Thank you for your feedback. We have added it.</p>
<p>In the manuscript, some protein like Akt is written in multiple formats. Please write any protein or pathway name in the same format throughout the manuscript. Carefully revise the whole manuscript.</p>	<p>Thank you for your feedback. We have corrected it in the revised manuscript.</p>
<p>Reviewer 2 Name: Anonymous Conflict of Interest: None Date of Reviewer's Comments: February 24, 2025 Date of Author Response: March 11, 2025</p>	
Reviewer Comments	Author Response
<p>Reviewer Recommendation: Revision Required Overview: The manuscript does a good job of summarizing the key findings on carnosic acid's anticancer potential in a concise and well-organized manner. The structured approach and the inclusion of multiple cancer types make it informative and useful for readers. The manuscript is well-organized and suitable for the journal, but it requires some revisions before acceptance. Below are some key areas for improvement:</p>	<p>Thank you for your valuable comment. We appreciate your complement and suggestions. We have improvised the manuscript according to your comments.</p>

In line 29: after author et al., there is a space before year. Correct this type of mistakes in whole paper.	Thank you for your feedback. We have corrected it in the revised manuscript.
Make a solid aim in the Introduction section because it is very important for short review.	Thank you for your feedback. We have tried to provide a solid aim in the introduction.
In line 69: Authors need to ensure that only the genus and species (<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>) are italicized, while the authority abbreviation (L.) remains in regular font.	Thank you for your feedback. We have corrected it.
line 81: Please clarify the full form of "COX" in for better readability.	Thank you for your feedback. We have clarified it.
Ensure that all abbreviations are introduced with their full form upon first mention before using the shortened version throughout the text.	Thank you for your feedback. We have introduced all abbreviations upon first mention.
Please include a statement on the novelty of the study and its limitations in the Results and Discussion section to strengthen the manuscript.	Thank you for your feedback. We have revised it according to your suggestion.
In Table 1, referencing the study by Su et al., 2016, the animal model is mentioned, but the group size and specific doses, including the route of administration, are not clearly provided. Could you please clarify the animal group size and ensure that the doses and route of administration are presented accurately?	Thank you for your feedback. We have added it.
In line 42: Change the word "abundant"	Thank you for your feedback. We have changed it.
I would suggest improving the grammar throughout the manuscript for clarity and readability. After addressing all the comments, including improving the grammar and ensuring compliance with the author guidelines and formatting, I believe the manuscript will be ready for publication.	Thank you for your feedback. We have revised the manuscript and tried to address all your comments and improvisation.

Round 2

Reviewer 1 Name: Anonymous Conflict of Interest: None Date of Reviewer's Comments: March 12, 2025 Date of Author Response: Not required	
Reviewer Comments	Author Response
Reviewer Recommendation: Accept Submission	-
Reviewer 2 Name: Anonymous Conflict of Interest: None Date of Reviewer's Comments: Not responded Date of Author Response: Not required	
Reviewer Comments	Author Response
Reviewer Recommendation: Not responded	-